

Frequency Reconfigurable Antennas for 5G application: A survey

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Abstract— The use of reconfigurable antennas is the demand of future 5G wireless communication. The reconfigurability can be achieved in frequency, polarization, radiation pattern, or it can also be achieved in any two parameters, like frequency and polarization OR polarization and radiation pattern OR frequency and radiation pattern. The different designs of the frequency reconfigurable types of antenna found in state of art beginning from concept of microstrip patch antennas towards reconfigurable designs of various types and microstrip antenna designs for 5G and also the designs of sub 6GHz band are discussed. The use of RF switches like PIN diodes, varactor diodes, MEMS switches, etc. along with well designed dc biasing circuit help in achieving reconfigurability. These switches help in achieving reconfigurability by changing the current distribution of the overall antenna structure.

Keywords— PIN diodes, MEMS switches, reconfigurability

I. INTRODUCTION

With the rapid development of wireless communication, especially the in-depth research on 5G, reconfigurable antennas is gaining great attention. Different characteristics (such as resonant frequency, radiation patterns, polarization, etc) of the antennas can be reconfigurable through the change of the structures. The concept of reconfigurable antenna firstly appeared in D.Schaubert's patent "Frequency-Agile, Polarization Diverse Microstrip Antenna and Frequency Scanned Arrays" in 1983[19]. In 1999, 12 well-known universities, research institutes and companies in the United States participate in the project of "Reconfigurable Aperture Program (RECAP)", launched by the United States Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency (DARPA). In the project, reconfigurable antennas were well researched and achieved some improvements to some extent in addition to their features like lighter in weight, smaller in dimension and lower in price[20]. So, although the research on reconfigurable antennas began just in recent years, it has already become the focus both at home and abroad. The reconfigurability can be achieved in terms of three parameters like frequency, polarization and radiation pattern exclusively or in combined manner. There are different designing approaches to achieve the reconfigurability in terms of frequency, polarization and radiation pattern. The different designs of microstrip antennas starting from microstrip antennas of all reconfigurability types towards 5G frequency reconfigurable designs in state of art is reported. The state of art is continued with the proposed design idea which will employ different methods studied in state of art.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

2.1 Microstrip Antennas with different types of reconfigurability

Microstrip antennas are used in high-performance applications because of their features like low profile, conformable to planar and non-planar surfaces, simple and inexpensive to manufacture using modern printed-circuit technology, mechanically robust when mounted on rigid surfaces, and when the particular patch shape and mode are selected, they are very versatile in terms of resonant frequency, polarization, pattern, and impedance. A microstrip antenna in its simplest form consists of a radiating patch on one side of a dielectric substrate and a ground plane on the other side. The radiating patch of microstrip antennas can

be square, rectangular, thin strip (dipole), circular, elliptical, triangular, or any other configuration. These and others are manifested in Figure 1, can also be photo-etched on the dielectric substrate. [2]

Fig. 1. Respective shapes of microstrip antenna[2]

The probe fed circularly polarized antennas with truncated corners are reported which benefit by availing no strict orientations between base station and mobile units [6]. The RFID reader antenna generally uses CP antenna, which can be probe fed, with truncated corners as well as with different slotted/slit microstrip structures [23]. Different ways of achieving polarization reconfigurability like employing truncated corners, probe fed method on the patch are reported in [18]. The polarization reconfigurability in terms of RHCP, LHCP, LP is reported, with a patch with diagonal rectangular slots along both diagonals, in which two couples (R & L) of switches are used to select active slots (L or R) [24]. A CP system is more suitable than a LP system as LP is insensitive to transmitter and receiver orientations [17]. Two orthogonal slots on a probe fed patch antenna and two PIN diodes on that to switch slots ON and OFF yields polarization diversity from LHCP to RHCP is reported in [7], which can be used in WLANs, Satellite links, space robots. The four different linear phased arrays, in which the element is designed with different phase shift, and the six RF-MEMS switches are placed in feed networks, has reported pattern reconfigurability, which can be used in wireless communication and satellite communication [22]. The combined reconfigurability in terms of frequency and polarization OR frequency and radiation pattern OR polarization and radiation pattern has also got different ways of designing. The use of RF switches is employed to achieve change in current distribution, thus resulting into reconfigurability in terms of frequency [1]

2.2 Microstrip Antenna with Switchable Frequency

Frequency reconfigurable antenna has the reconfiguration of the resonant frequency by the change of the structure, while the radiation patterns and polarization remain unchanged. So, frequency reconfigurable antenna can be applied among a very wide arrangement of frequency band or among multiple frequency bands [1].

Microstrip patch with dual patch elements and two parallel C-slots on patch elements employed on it is reported in [3], as shown in Fig. 2. The two PIN diode switches are placed on connecting lines of simple feed networks to patch elements. Dual band mode is achieved by switching ON either one of the two patch elements while wide band mode is achieved by switching ON both patch elements. The main patch with four sub-patches and ground plane if employed gives five frequency bands is reported in [4], in which varactor diodes at each of the sub-patch inputs is employed which helps in achieving frequency reconfigurability.

Fig. 2. Configuration of dual patch antenna with dc biasing networks[3]

With the advent of multiband wireless communication systems, reconfigurable antennas with the frequency selective characteristic have received much attention recently. A reconfigurable antenna with the polarization diversity function is needed to switch the linear polarization signal received from gap-filler and right hand circular polarization signal received directly from the satellite in satellite communication systems. The U-slot inserted into square patch and PIN diode is placed on it as shown in Fig. 3. The PIN diode when made ON and OFF give frequency diversity. The PIN diodes are placed on truncated corners of square patch. These PIN diodes when made ON and OFF help in giving polarization diversity. [5]

Fig. 3. Frequency and polarization reconfigurable antenna design [5]

Two microstrip line fed monopoles printed on 1.6mm thick substrate with a dielectric constant of 2.2, sharing a common partial ground gives resonance in UWB range, and also gives frequency reconfigurability [15]. Equilateral triangular microstrip antennas with switchable resonant frequency is demonstrated by loading a pair of slits in the triangular patch and two PIN diodes utilized in it to switch the slits ON and OFF[16].

The diversity in functionality of reconfigurable antennas is usually implemented by introducing a tuning mechanism, known as switching, which alters the shape of the radiating structure to achieve both versatility and reliability in providing an efficient wireless link for various wireless applications. Electronic, mechanical or optical switching may be employed while building reconfigurable antennas. However, electronic tunability is found to be frequently used because of its efficiency and reliability especially in dynamic bandwidth allocation. Electronic reconfigurability is often attained by getting switching components, such as PIN diodes, FET transistors or RF MEMS switches distributed in a predetermined manner depending on the implementation requirements along with the antenna structure. [1]

2.3 Microstrip Antenna with Switchable Frequency for generalized 5G application

A comparative analysis of most demanded future 5G mm wave reconfigurable wireless generation network antenna is reported in [8]. A GCPW fed millimeter-wave frequency reconfigurable antennas designed as shown in Fig.4 is studied. Through variable resistors, shifting in resonance frequency in 58-62GHz band is achieved. Variable resistors are used to achieve reconfigurability. Microstrip line feed and Ground coplanar waveguide feeding technique(GCPW) are used. Effects of slot position, slot length and

feed position is investigated and analysed on return loss, bandwidth and frequency ratio for four different models.[8]

Fig. 4. mmwave frequency reconfigurable antenna[8]

A 2-element MIMO antenna system has been presented in [9] for wireless handheld devices operating at microwave and mmwave bands which has a dual-functional slot antenna designed to work as a frequency-reconfigurable slot antenna at 4G band and also has connected slot antenna array at 5G band.

A new differential-fed frequency reconfigurable antenna for WLAN and Sub-6GHz 5G applications is presented which is basically designed with a combination of proximity-coupled technique, stacked structure and differential-fed technology. It can operate at 2.45GHz or 3.50GHz by controlling the states of four PIN diode switches directly driven by bias networks. Four identical DC biasing circuits as shown in Fig. 5 are applied to control four PIN diodes, in which two inductors are employed to prevent AC signal on antenna from leaking into bias circuit. [10] The complete antenna is simulated using HFSS [14].

Fig. 5. DC bias circuit [10]

A miniaturized and multi-band reconfigurable slot antenna suitable for 5G smartphone with metal casing application is presented, in which the small antenna size and wide operating bandwidth are obtained by folding the slot and introducing two PIN diodes [11].

A simple, planar frequency reconfigurable mobile handset antenna is presented which has very simple design and is with two dipole radiators. The designed antenna provides gain over 4dB in both resonance modes and more than 70% efficiency in entire operation bandwidth. The PIN diodes in forward bias offer a resistance of 0.85 ohm and reverse bias capacitance of 0.21 pF. The biasing network employed for PIN diodes has 3 chip inductors and one chip capacitor to maintain proper isolation between RF supply and DC biasing. The paper presents a simple and effective frequency reconfigurable cognitive antenna for 5G applications in the sub-6GHz band [12]. A new reconfigurable MIMO antenna array is introduced for 4G/5G which contains four elements of C-shaped slot antennas along with PIN diode switches. The operation frequency of the reconfigurable radiators can be switched from 2.4-2.8 GHz to 3-4 GHz [13].

III. PROPOSED METHOD

The idea is to design a novel microstrip patch antenna which will reconfigure in multiband in the 5G sub-6 GHz band. The Microstrip antenna will be designed in sub 6 GHz band and then on it, U slot will be inserted on which two PIN diodes will be placed which will allow change of structure, thus giving change in current distribution resulting in frequency reconfigurability. The proposed design of microstrip antenna will be as shown in Fig. 6. below which clearly shows inserted U slot on microstrip patch antenna. The simulation of the proposed design is done in HFSS V 19. Once the resonance is achieved in multiband by changing the status of PIN diodes from ON to OFF and vice versa, the next task is to design a DC bias circuit for the PIN diodes, which will help in sourcing the diodes. The future task is to optimize the design in simulation for sub-6GHz band. The realization of PIN diodes can be done using lumped RLC elements in the simulation software HFSS, whose value of resistance and capacitance can be varied to indicate the change of status of RF switches.

Fig. 6. Proposed Design Of Frequency Reconfigurable Antenna For 5g Application

IV. CONCLUSION

The frequency reconfigurability can be achieved by constructing U-slots or C-slots along with RF switches installed on the slots, which help in changing the current distribution of the complete antenna structure. The dc biasing of RF switches is to be done properly to maintain the expected resonance characteristics. The switching of RF switches from ON to OFF state or vice versa will help achieving the frequency reconfigurability phenomenon. The transition status of RF switches actually results in change in structures which leads to change in current distribution on the patch surface thus resulting into frequency reconfigurability. The state of art can be used to design the proposed 5G frequency reconfigurable antenna to be operated in sub 6GHz band. The proposed design of sub 6GHz band can be used in wireless communication.

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